

THE RELIABILITY AND THE VALIDITY STUDY OF THE INTERNAL MARKETING SCALE IN SPORTS

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ABSTRACT

Study aim(s): This research aimed to develop an internal marketing scale specific to sports organizations to evaluate the effect of the internal marketing perception of active participants working in sports organizations on the employee.

Methods: Since this research was a scale development study aimed to reveal the internal marketing perception of sports service business employees, the research was basic since the quantitative evaluation was applied to the data collected from the participants, the research was performed according to the general screening model. The universe of the research consists of volunteer individuals who have at least 3 years of professional experience in sports service enterprises in Istanbul. The sample consists of 297 voluntary participants. The obtained data were transferred to the SPSS 25 package program, exploratory factor analysis, and confirmatory factor analysis were applied through Lisrel version 8.80.

Results: It has been determined that the internal marketing scale in sports organizations, which was developed to determine the perceptions of sports service employees towards internal marketing practices, consists of 17 items and 2 sub-dimensions, and is a valid and reliable measurement tool.

Conclusions: It has been concluded that the scale is a valid and reliable scale that can be used to determine the internal marketing perceptions of sports service employees.

Keywords: Internal Marketing, Sports Business, Internal Marketing in Sport

INTRODUCTION

Businesses aiming to survive in an increasingly competitive environment due to developing technology have to show a difference without a doubt. Businesses in the service sector, on the other hand, demonstrate this difference with their internal marketing approach, in which they value their employees at least as much as their customers. The understanding of internal marketing is to ensure that the goals of the enterprise and the goals of the employee achieve success by making them a common goal. Employees who feel valuable, important, and happy in the business achieve satisfaction of their work by adopting the service or product they offered. The internal customer at the point of satisfaction represents a committed and motivated employee. The quality of the service to be received by the external customer and, followingly, the duration of his/her stay in the organization depends on the satisfaction of the internal customer. The performance of the happy internal customer contributes positively to the quality of the service or product offered to the external customer [1].

Sports businesses are one of the leading sectors in which customer relationship is intertwined in the service sector. Employees of sports businesses, who are in constant contact with external customers, are at the forefront of the service sectors in which the internal marketing approach should be applied successfully. The internal marketing perception adopted by sports businesses that require constant and intense contact between the customer and the employee is of great importance in terms of customer satisfaction and continuity. The internal customer, who is well motivated and has adopted the organizational culture, has a more active and positive approach towards the external customer. While this positive effect is reflected in the quality of the service or product that the external customer receives from the sports business, this situation contributes to the customer's loyal behavior towards the business. Thus, the fact that ensuring customer satisfaction, supporting teamwork and adapting employees to change with

training reveals the importance of the internal marketing approach.

Today, the internal marketing approach applied by sports businesses, whose effectiveness is increasing in the service sector, greatly increases in the market. For sports businesses to survive in an increasingly competitive environment due to developing technology and to ensure their continuity in the market without losing their effectiveness depending on the changing service understanding, sports businesses should create an internal marketing strategy specific to their employees. Followingly, it was wondered how and at what level the perceptions, attitudes, and behaviors of business employees towards internal marketing practices. In this context, this study aimed to contribute to the literature by developing a valid and reliable internal marketing scale in sports to determine and measure the attitudes and behaviors related to the internal marketing perception of sports service business employees.

METHODS

Research design

This research aimed to develop an internal marketing scale specific to sports organizations to evaluate the effect of the internal marketing perception of active participants working in sports organizations on the employee. Since this research was a scale development study aimed at revealing the internal marketing perception of sports service business employees, the research was basic since the quantitative evaluation was applied to the data collected from the participants, the research was performed according to the general screening model. The survey model is “a research model that aims to describe a past or present situation as it is and tries to define the individual, event or object that is the subject of the research as it is in its own conditions” [2]. Data were collected online on a voluntary survey technique as the data collection method.

Study sample

The universe of the research consisted of volunteer individuals who had at least 3 years of professional experience in sports service enterprises in Istanbul. The sampling method to be used as the simple random sampling method, in which all the employees had an equal and random chance of entering the sample, and at the same time, the research results were revealed quickly and easily [3]. SA simple random sampling method was preferred as the sampling method. In the validity and reliability studies of the scale, it was stated that the sample size should be five times the number of items or observed variables for the study group to use the factor analysis technique [4]. According to Kline [5], it was recommended to keep the item (variable) ratio (10:1) for the sample size, but it was stated that this ratio can be reduced, but it should be at least 26 (2:1). In this context, there were 27 questions in the internal marketing scale of sports organizations. Therefore, the sample size taken from the universe was determined as (n: 297). Participants voluntarily participated in the study by reading the informed volunteer form.

Table 1. Socio-Demographical Characteristics of the Participants

	Groups	N	%
Age	18-26	84	28.4
	27-35	122	41.2
	36-44	61	20.6
	45 and older	29	9.8
	Total	296	100.0
Gender	Female	131	44.3
	Male	165	55.7
	Total	296	100.0
Professional Experience	3-6 Years	182	61.5
	7-10 Years	78	26.4
	11 years and more	36	12.2
	Total	296	100.0

When Table 1 was evaluated; it was determined that 28,4% of the participants were between the ages of 18-26, 41,2% were between the ages of 27-35, 20,6% were between the ages of 36-44, and 9,8% were aged 45 and over. Besides, 44,3% of the participants were female participants and 55,7% were male participants. It was determined that 61,5% of the participants have 3-6 years of professional experience, 26,4% have 7-10 years of professional experience and 12,2% have 11 years or more of professional experience.

Establishment of Internal Marketing Scale Item Pool in Sports Organizations

During the creation of the item pool; Current and internationally accepted studies related to the research subject were screened, and the questions and topics that would be the subject of the scale study and the themes were determined. A general evaluation [6-9] was performed following similar scales and dimensions in the studies conducted in this field at home and abroad on internal marketing, and a specific 55-item question pool regarding internal marketing was created. Interrogative sentences to be selected in a foreign language were translated into Turkish by experts who have a good command of the subject and know the language of the question and turned into interrogative sentences to be used in the scale. In the question pool created according to the internal marketing dimensions, the item distributions according to the dimensions were not subjected to a proportional calculation.

Expert opinions and scope validity

In the second stage of the research, the created form was submitted to the opinion of 3 experts, who were knowledgeable in the subject area and were informed about the study subject, to receive expert opinions. With the help of feedback from experts, a candidate scale was tried to be created. Moreover, to get the opinions of the experts, a 3-point rating was used. In the prepared form, experts were asked to

choose one of the options "appropriate", "partially appropriate" or "inappropriate" for each item. By combining all of the questionnaires in a single form, it was determined how many experts approved the possible options for each item. The questions to which three experts answered as "inappropriate" were directly excluded, the questions that were answered as "partially appropriate" were reevaluated, and the questions that received the "appropriate" answer were kept constant. The questions that were not removed from the pool and corrected were presented to the experts for their opinions. Regarding the opinions of the experts in this process, the content validity of the items was determined by the content validity rate developed by Veneziano and Hooper [10, 11]. The ratios in question were determined by taking the ratio of the total number of experts who gave positive answers to each item to the total number of experts, minus one. For the content validity indices of the items, the number of experts and the values of the obtained content validity rate was determined. Items with a content validity ratio of less than 0,80 were excluded from the study. In total, 27 questions in the question pool were evaluated positively by the experts. Participants were asked to express their perceptions on a 5-point Likert-type scale ranging from "I totally agree", "I agrvee", "I partially agree", "I do not agree" and "I strongly disagree" to the scale questions created in line with the calculations of the content validity ratios obtained. Finally, the scale questions were sent to a Turkish specialist to be examined in terms of spelling and grammar. Necessary corrections were performed as suggested. The scale has taken its final form.

Data analysis

Explanatory and confirmatory factor analyzes were applied through IBM SPSS 25 and Lisrel 8.80 package program to test the validity and reliability of internal marketing questions in sports organizations consisting of 27 questions. Statistically, $p < 0,05$ was considered statistically significant.

FINDINGS

Construct validity studies with exploratory factor analysis

Table 2. The skewness-kurtosis values of the scale questions and the results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test significance level

Items	n	Skewness	Kurtosis	P
Item 1	296	-,642	-,528	,000
Item 2	296	-,698	-,473	,000
Item 3	296	-,730	-,396	,000
Item 4	296	-,617	-,627	,000
Item 5	296	-,203	-,899	,000
Item 6	296	-,194	-,735	,000
Item 7	296	-,748	-,380	,000
Item 8	296	-,747	-,381	,000
Item 9	296	-,576	-,465	,000
Item 10	296	-,676	-,440	,000
Item 11	296	-,263	,969	,000
Item 12	296	-,936	,648	,000
Item 13	296	-,217	-,605	,000
Item 14	296	-,472	-,782	,000
Item 15	296	,199	-,251	,000
Item 16	296	,242	-,134	,000
Item 17	296	-,941	478	,000

When the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test results were examined, it was seen that the deviations from normality in the scale questions were at significant levels. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was only one of the methods used to evaluate the normality state. It was determined that there were no excessive deviations in the normal distribution curves, and all scores were within the range of ± 1 considering the skewness and kurtosis coefficients. Büyüköztürk [12] stated that these values were within the ± 1 range, and Tabachnick and Fidell [13] stated that if the skewness coefficients were between $\pm 1,5$, the data showed normal distribution. It was determined that the skewness-kurtosis values of the scores were in the range of $\pm 1 / \pm 1,5$, there were no excessive deviations in the normal

distribution curves, and the data showed a normal distribution. It was decided to apply Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) to the scale developed in this direction.

In the factor analysis, when the "direct oblimin" rotation method was applied, it was determined that the coefficients in the correlation matrix between the variables were less than 0,05. In this direction, the "varimax" rotation method was chosen and applied again.

Table 3. Direct oblimin rotation (Component Correlation Matrix)

Factors	1. Dimension	2. Dimension
1. Dimension	1,000	,467
2. Dimension	,467	1,000

*Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
 Rotation Method: Oblimin with Kaiser Normalization.*

In the factor analysis, when the "direct oblimin" rotation method was applied, it was determined that the coefficients in the correlation matrix between the variables were less than 0,05. In this direction, the "varimax" rotation method was chosen and applied again. When the item-total correlation values were examined, it was seen that the item-total correlation values of the expressions in the factor 1 dimension are between $r=0,708$ and $r=0,828$, and the expressions in the factor 2 dimension were between $r=0,643$ and $r=0,729$ (Appendix 2). It showed that the obtained values had the distinguishing feature of the expressions in the scale.

In the Exploratory Factor Analysis applied, "KMO and Bartlett's" test values were found to be higher than 0,05 (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy, 0,914). Accordingly, it was assumed that the number of samples included in the study was sufficient. "Bartlett's Test of Sphericity" values were also found to be suitable for the application of Confirmatory Factor Analysis ($p<0,05$).

Table 4. KMO and Bartlett's test indicates the adequacy of the sample size

KMO	,914
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Bartlett's Test	X ²	3784,748
	Sd	136
	p	,000

In the Exploratory Factor Analysis applied, "KMO and Bartlett's" test values were found to be higher than 0,05 (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy= ,914). Accordingly, it was assumed that the number of samples included in the study was sufficient. A statistically significant relationship was determined between the items in the dimensions explained according to Bartlett's Test of Sphericity values ($p<0,05$). Therefore, "Bartlett's Test of Sphericity" values were found to be suitable for the application of Confirmatory Factor Analysis ($p<0,05$). With the load analysis, the load to the dimension (latent factor) in which the items were explained was specified. In the determination of the explained factors (latent factor), the "eigenvalues" value was accepted as higher than 1.

Table 5. Communalities to the latent factor in which the items were explained

Items	Disclosure rate
Business management tries to understand employees and offers solutions for them.	,658
The company provides the opportunity to easily convey employee expectations and complaints.	,632
The company regularly allows its employees to express themselves.	,682
The company adopts a management approach in which employees have the right to speak.	,723
The company applies special performance and motivation-enhancing systems to its employees regarding their departments.	,704
The company demonstrates an understanding of problem solving.	,707

Business management deals with the problems of the employees.	,624
Our managers have information about employee performance.	,525
Employees can express their opinions impartially about the services offered.	,670
I have the opportunity to freely share ideas and criticize opinions at work (in the department).	,647
Respect for employees and customers is essential in the business.	,481
Employees in the company have good relations with each other.	,418
The company has the understanding that a competitive environment should be created to increase the performance of the employees.	,362
Our company offers social support packages (birth, marriage, etc.) to its employees.	,278
Various performance-based reward systems are implemented in our company.	,733
Salaries and bonuses in our company are according to performance.	,650
Employees learn about in-company information and announcements in the fastest way and at the same time.	,506

When the table below was examined, it was determined that the load ratio to the latent factor was higher than 500. Moreover, “Respect for employees and customers is essential in the business” (,481), “The company has the understanding that a competitive environment should be created to increase the performance of the employees” (,362), and “Our company offers social support packages (birth, marriage, etc.) to its employees” factors were

determined that the load rate of the items (,278) was less than (,500).

Table 6. Item-total correlation item values

Items	Factor 1	Items	Factor 2
Item 1	,824**	Item 11	,553**
Item 2	,812**	Item 12	,634**
Item 3	,828**	Item 13	,644**
Item 4	,864**	Item 14	,630**
Item 5	,823**	Item 15	,768**
Item 6	,821**	Item 16	,672**
Item 7	,719**	Item 17	,659**
Item 8	,666**		
Item 9	,810**		
Item 10	,806**		

N: 296; *p=0,05;**p=0,001

To determine the internal consistency of the scale, the item-total correlation coefficient should be calculated. It is stated that the item-total correlation coefficient will determine the discrimination of the items by revealing the relationship between the item scores in the scale and the total scores of the items [14]. In the item-total score correlation analysis performed to evaluate the internal consistency of the scale, it was stated that high correlation coefficients indicate that the relevant item had high compliance with the measured theoretical structure and the correlation coefficient should be 0,30 and above [15,16]. Because the item-total correlation coefficient of the scale determines the distinctiveness, items with values of 0,40 and higher were well in terms of distinctiveness, values between 0,30 and 0,40 were good, and values between 0,20 and 0,30 were considered appropriate. Items and values of 0,20 or less were determined as items that should be excluded from the study [17]. It was determined that the correlation values varied between 0,719 and 0,864 in factor 1, and between 0,553 and 0,768 in factor 2. It was understood that each item in the factors is in a significant and positive

relationship with the whole of the relevant factor, and the item discrimination feature was found very well.

Figure 1. Line graph of the scale

Table 7. The explained total variance of latent factors

Factors	First			Disclosure Sums			Rotation Sums		
	Eigenvalues			of Square Loads			of Square Loads		
	T	V %	C%	T	V%	C %	T	V %	C%
1	8,	49,	49,	8,	49,	49,	5,	35,	35,
	46	77	77	46	77	77	97	16	16
2	1,	9,0	58,	1,	9,0	58,	4,	23,	58,
	53	4	82	53	4	82	02	65	82

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis. T1: total, V%: Variance %, C%: Cumulative %, T: Total

With the load analysis, the load to the dimension (latent factor) in which the items were explained was specified. In the determination of the explained factors (latent factor), the "eigenvalues" value was accepted as higher than 1. Based on this, the variables explained in more than one factor with a difference of less than 1 were evaluated as ineffective and removed. And for this reason, after applying "varimax" repeatedly (25 times) for each item whose rotation was removed, two latent factors with a cumulative value of 58,8 were explained.

According to the eigenvalue form given above, two factors with "eigenvalues" higher than 1 were explained.

Table 8. The items of the explained latent factors (Rotated Component Matrix)

R	D	Questions	Factors	
			1	2
1		Business management tries to understand employees and offers solutions for them.		,668
2		The company provides the opportunity to easily convey employee expectations and complaints.		,694
3		The company regularly allows its employees to express themselves.		,714
7		The company adopts a management approach in which employees have the right to speak.		,695
10		Business management deals with the problems of the employees.		,786
11		Our managers have information about employee performance.		,720
12		Employees can express their opinions impartially about the services offered.		,715
13		I have the opportunity to freely share ideas and criticize opinions at work (in the department).		,690
14		Respect for employees and customers is essential in the business.		,692

Latent factor (dimensions): First latent factor (size)

15	Employees in the company have good relations with each other.	,590
8	The company has the understanding that a competitive environment should be created to increase the performance of the employees.	,663
9	The company demonstrates an understanding of problem solving.	,663
19	The company has the understanding that a competitive environment should be created to increase the performance of the employees.	,571
22	Our company offers social support packages (birth, marriage, etc.) to its employees.	,440
23	Various performance-based reward systems are implemented in our company.	,851
24	Salaries and bonuses in our company are according to performance.	,803
25	Employees learn about in-company information and announcements in the fastest way and at the same time.	,616

Latent factor (dimensions):: The second latent factor (size)

were evaluated as ineffective and were removed. In the first rotation of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis, 4 latent factors or dimensions were explained with a cumulative value of 64%. Variables explained with a difference of less than 1 in more than one factor were removed one by one. And for this reason, "varimax" was applied repeatedly (25 times) for each item whose rotation was removed. As a result of the analysis, the 4 factors explained by removing items 4, 5, 6, 16, 17, 18, 20, 21, 26, and 27, decreased to 2 factors. In this direction; While the first dimension of the scale was composed of 1, 2, 3, 7, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, and 15 items, the second dimension of the scale consisted of 8, 9, 19, 22, 23, 24, 25 items.

Table 9. Reliability of the items in the explained dimensions of the scale

Factors				Total Scale	
Dimension 1		Dimension 2		C_a	items
C_a	Items	C_a	Items		
,923	10	,842	7	,933	17

C_a : Cronbach's Alpha

A reliability test was applied for factor analysis applied to test the reliability of the items in the explained dimensions of the scale. As a result of the test, the Cronbach's Alpha value of the items in the first dimension of the scale was 0,923, the Cronbach's

R: Rank, D: Dimensions, Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 3 iterations.

In the rotated component matrix, values less than ,30 were not counted as significant and therefore were not included. Variables that were explained in more than one factor with differences of less than 1

Figure 2. Significance levels of perceived organizational support pathway chart

Figure 3. The diagram obtained after the modification

Alpha value in the second dimension was 0,842, and the Cronbach's Alpha value of the scale total score was 0,933. For scale reliability studies, the internal consistency coefficient was checked.

Figure 4. Path diagram error variances obtained after modification

A high Cronbach Alpha coefficient was an important indicator of validity, as well as showing that the sample was homogeneous within and the scale items were compatible with each other [18]. Interpretation of the internal consistency coefficient was “unreliable if it was below 0,40, low reliability if it was between 0,40-0,59, reliable between 0,60-0,79 and high reliability between 0,80-1,00” [19]. It was understood that the sub-dimensions of the scale and the internal consistency coefficients of the total score had high reliability.

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was applied to test the determined two-factor structure of the scale.

In Figure 2, the value of χ^2/sd , one of the fit indices the model, and was determined as 5,63. A Chi-Square (Chi-Square)/degrees-of-freedom ratio (df) below 3 in the CFA corresponds to a perfect fit, and a score below 5 corresponds to a moderate fit [20,21]. For the analysis performed followingly, the χ^2/sd ratio did not give a perfect and moderate fit. Besides, the NFI value, which was one of the fit indices, was 0,92; the NNFI value was 0,89; the GFI value was 0,89 CFI value was 0,92; The AGFI value was found to be 0,80.

An RMSEA value of less than 0,05 indicates an excellent fit, and a value of less than 0,08 indicated a good fit [22]. The RMSEA value did not fit well or perfectly with the 0,123 level.

In this context, it was seen that the fit index obtained for the first analysis was weak. At this stage of the analysis, it was useful to evaluate the modification suggestions. When the modification suggestions were examined; It was seen that if the modifications will be made between IP8 and IP9, IP10 and IP11 and IP23 and IP24, will contribute to the fit indices. Three different modification processes were applied.

In Figure 3, the t-values of the latent variable explaining the observed variables were shown on the arrows. Parameter estimates were significant at the 0,05 level if t-values exceed 1,96. In the analysis performed following the structural equation model, non-significant t values should be excluded from the analysis [22]. In this context, when the t-values in Figure 9 were examined; It was seen that the results were between 8,05 and 18,89, and all the items presented a significant t-value.

It was useful to control the error variances in confirmatory factor analyses, and the results regarding error variances were expected to be low [22]. The error variance showed the unexplained part of the variance of the data set [12].

In the literature, many fit indices are used to determine the fit adequacy of the model tested in CFA. The most commonly used fit indices were the Chi-Square Fit Test (Chi-Square Goodness), Goodness of Fit Index (GFI), Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Normed Fit Index (NFI), Non-Normed Fit Index (NNFI), Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR), and Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA). Since the fit indices had strengths and weaknesses in evaluating the fit between the theoretical model and the real data, it was

recommended to use many fit index values to reveal the fit of the model.

When the fit indices obtained after the modification was examined; The value of χ^2/sd , one of the fit indices of the model, was determined as 2,82.

Moreover, the NFI value, which was one of the fit indices, was 0,97; the NNFI value was 0,98, the IFI value was 0,98, the RFI value was 0,96, the CFI value was 0,98, the GFI value was 0,89, and the AGFI value was found to be 0,85. As a result of confirmatory factor analysis, a factor structure of the scale showed a good fit. The RMSEA value of 0,075 showed that it gave acceptable and valid results. The RMR was determined to be 0,042. When these results were compared to the standard fit criteria that was to be checked as a result of the confirmatory factor analysis stated in the study of Schermelleh-Engel and Moosbrugger [23] in Table 10 below, it was seen that the general fit values were in the "perfect fit values" group.

Table 10. Fit values for the scale

	Acceptable Fit	Perfect Fit	VRS
NFI	=0,90 and above	=0,95 and above	0,97
NNFI	=0,90 and above	=0,95 and above	0,98
IFI	=0,90 and above	=0,95 and above	0,98
RFI	=0,90 and above	=0,95 and above	0,96
CFI	=0,95 and above	=0,97 and above	0,98
GFI	=0,85 and above	=0,90 and above	0,89
AGFI	=0,85 and üzeri	=0,90 and above	0,85
RMR	=0,80 and <0,08	=0,50 and <0,050	0,067
REMSEA	=0,80 and <0,08	=0,50 and <0,050	0,079
$\chi^2/df = 2,82$			

VRS: Value regarding the scale

A Chi-Square (Chi-Square)/degrees-of-freedom ratio (df) of less than 3 in CFA corresponds to a perfect fit and a score of less than 5 corresponds to a moderate fit [20, 21]. For the analysis performed in this direction, the χ^2/sd ratio showed that it was a perfect fit. An RMSEA value of less than 0,05 indicated a perfect fit, and a value of less than 0,08

indicated a good fit [22]. The RMSEA value was in acceptable agreement with the 0,079 level. Thus, it can be said that the 17-item and two-factor structure of the internal marketing scale in sports organizations was confirmed as a model. As a result of exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis, factors, in other words, dimensions were tried to be named. At this stage, the contents of the items were considered. The order of the dimensions was obtained by ordering the item numbers from smallest to largest.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This study includes a scale development process performed to determine the views of sports business employees on internal marketing perception. The validity and reliability study of the scale was applied to 296 participants working in sports businesses.

As a result of the development processes of the internal marketing scale in sports organizations, the validity and reliability studies of the scale were performed and reported. Explanatory and confirmatory factor analysis was performed within the scope of the scale's construct validity. Before the exploratory factor analysis, the suitability of the data for factor analysis was analyzed with the KMO and Barlett tests, and the KMO value was found to be 0,914.

KMO values reveal whether the value of a variable in the scale can be adequately predicted by other variables. For this reason, a value above 0,90 indicated that the value was perfect [24,19]. It was understood that the value obtained in the research was at a perfect level.

After determining the suitability of the scale items for factor analysis, exploratory factor analysis was performed on the data obtained to reveal the scale's construct validity. In the factor analysis application, the maximum direct oblimin method was chosen to ensure that the structure of the relationship between the factors remained the same. As a result of the factor analysis, a scale consisting of 17 items was

obtained by eliminating the items with a factor load of less than 0,30. In the factor analysis, the items were gathered under 2 factors with a total explained variance of 58,821% and an eigenvalue higher than 1. This result meets the values determined in the literature [13, 22, 24].

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was performed and fit indices (FI) were examined to see if the model agreed or was inconsistent with the data. As a result of the analysis; The value of χ^2/sd , one of the fit indices of the model, was determined as 2,82. Besides, the NFI value, which was one of the fit indices, was 0,97; the NNFI value was 0,98; the IFI value was 0,98, the RFI value was 0,96, the CFI value was 0,98, the GFI value was 0,89, and the AGFI value was found to be 0,85. As a result of confirmatory factor analysis, a factor structure of the scale showed a good fit. An RMSEA value of 0,075 showed that it gave acceptable and valid results.

Finally, the reliability values of the scale were examined and Cronbach's Alpha values were found to be ,933 when the perception dimension towards the enterprise (Cronbach's Alpha= ,923), the productivity dimension (Cronbach's Alpha= ,842) and the "Cronbach's Alpha" value of the whole scale was examined. The 1st, 2nd, 3rd, 4th, 5th, 6th, 7th, 8th, 9th, and 10th items in the scale constitute the perception dimension of the business, and all of these items were the attitude of the employees towards the business activities. It was seen that this dimension was related to the perception of the business since it was oriented toward the company and its behaviors. While the 11th, 12th, 13th, 14th, 15th, 16th, and 17th items comprised the productivity dimension, the second dimension was named productivity since all of these items included the keywords performance, motivation, and reward. The scale was graded as a 5-point Likert scale. The highest score to be obtained from the perception dimension of the scale was 50, the lowest score was 10, the highest score from the productivity sub-dimension was 35 and the lowest was 7 points.

As a result of the reliability and validity analysis performed, the “Internal Marketing Scale in Sports Organizations” consisting of a total of 17 items and 2 sub-factors was developed. It is thought that this scale, which has developed with this aspect, will contribute to the studies aimed at determining the perceptions of individuals working in sports businesses about the internal marketing practices of businesses.

REFERENCES

1. Chi CG, Gursoy D. "Employee Satisfaction, Customer Satisfaction, And Financial Performance: An Empirical Examination", *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 2009;28(2):245–253. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2008.08.003>.
2. Karasar N. *Bilimsel araştırma yöntemi*. Ankara: Nobel Yayın Dağıtım; 2008.
3. Yazıcıoğlu Y, Erdoğan S. *SPSS uygulamalı bilimsel araştırma yöntemleri*. Ankara: Detay Yayıncılık; 2004.
4. Child D. *The essentials of factor analysis*. London: A&C Black, 2006.
5. Kline P. *An easy guide to factor analysis*. New York: Routledge; 1994.
6. Chang CS, Chang HC. Perceptions of internal marketing and organizational commitment by nurses. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 2008; 65(1): 92–100.
7. Gounaris S. Internal-market orientation and its measurements. *Journal of Business Research*, 2006; 59: 432-448.
8. Liao JF. *The effects of internal marketing on customer orientation in the banking industry* (Doktora Tezi), Golden Gate University, San Fransisco; 2009.
9. Uygun M, Güner E, Mete S. Hizmet işletmelerinde iç müşteri yaklaşımının çalışanların müşteri yönlü davranış geliştirmesindeki rolü. *Organizasyon ve Yönetim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 2013; 5(1): 129-149.
10. Veneziano L, Hooper JA. method for quantifying content validity of health-related questionnaires. *American Journal of Health Behavior*. 1997; 21(1): 67-70.
11. Yurdagül H. *Ölçek Geliştirme Çalışmalarında Kapsam Geçerlik İndeksinin Kullanımı*. 14. Eğitim Bilimleri Kongresi, Pamukkale Üniversitesi, Denizli, 2005.
12. Büyüköztürk Ş. *Faktör analizi: Temel kavramlar ve ölçek geliştirmede kullanımı*. *Kuram ve Uygulamada Eğitim Yönetimi*, 2002;32(32): 470-483.
13. Tabachnick BG, Fidell LS. *Using multivariate statistics*. Boston, MA: Pearson/ Allyn; 2013.
14. Erkuş A. *Psikometri Üzerine Yazılar*. 1. Baskı. Ankara, Türk Psikologlar Derneği Yayınları; 2003.
15. Gözüm S, Aksayan S. Kültürlerarası ölçek uyarlaması için rehber II: Psikometrik özellikler ve kültürlerarası karşılaştırma. *Hemşirelikte Araştırma Geliştirme Dergisi*, 2002;4 (2): 9-20.
16. Özdamar K. *Paket Programlar ile İstatistiksel Veri Analizi I*. 5. Baskı, Kaan Kitabevi, Eskişehir; 2004.
17. Büyüköztürk Ş. *Sosyal Bilimler İçin Veri Analizi El Kitabı* (21. Baskı). Ankara: Pegem Akademi Yayınları; 2015.
18. Tavşancıl E. *Tutumların Ölçülmesi ve SPSS ile Veri Analizi*, Ankara: Nobel Akademik Yayıncılık; 2014.
19. Özdamar K. *Eğitim, Sağlık ve Davranış Bilimlerinde Ölçek ve Test Geliştirme Yapısal Eşitlik Modellemesi*, (1. bs.). Eskişehir: Nisan Kitabevi; 2016.
20. Kline RB. *Principles and practice of structural equation modeling*. New York: Guilford Press; 2005.
21. Sümer N. Yapısal eşitlik modelleri: Temel kavramlar ve örnek uygulamalar. *Türk Psikoloji Yazıları*, 2000; 3 (6): 49-74.
22. Çokluk Ö, Şekercioğlu G, Büyüköztürk Ş. *Sosyal Bilimler İçin Çok Değişkenli İstatistik: SPSS ve LISREL Uygulamaları*. Ankara: Pegem Akademi, 2012.
23. Schermelleh-Engel K, Moosbrugger H. Evaluating the fit of structural equation models: Tests of significance and descriptive goodness-of-fit

measures. *Methods of Psychological Research Online*, 2003;8 (2): 23-74.

24. Seer İ. *Psikolojik test geliřtirme ve uyarlama sũreci SPSS ve Lisrel uygulamaları*. Ankara: Anı Yayıncılık; 2015.

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